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Care in Ruination: accessing children's critiques of health through playwriting.

ABSTRACT

Using two plays written by girls and boys, I discuss how children from low-income urban neighborhoods in Honduras reflected on the slow process of privatization of the Honduran national health system. The children peppered their narratives with motifs suggestive of ongoing processes of material and social deterioration under capitalism, while paying attention to the different social mechanisms through which care could be mobilized. The plays speak to the value of incorporating children's perspectives on topics of health-disease processes that circle political, economic, and social tensions, and the importance of incorporating new ways of producing knowledge through artistic mediums.

KEYWORDS: Honduras, children, imaginal caring, public health, playwriting, ruination

Media teaser: What informs children's understanding of public health systems? How do children relate economic processes to experiences with public health services?

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In this article I address 1) how children's understandings and experiences of public health are shaped by local political-economic contexts and histories, and 2) how children relate complex information about local health-disease processes. Anthropologists that research alongside children have addressed the importance of co-constructing knowledge with participants and stakeholders to, among other things, give participants a stake in the production of knowledge and to produce knowledge that may otherwise lie beyond the realm of awareness of the researcher (Pfister, Vindrola-Padros, and Johnson 2014). The data co-constructed by children and researchers is complex (Johnson, Pfister, and Vindrola-Padros 2012; Pfister, Vindrola-Padros, and Johnson 2014) and demonstrate that children are both aware of many of the social dynamics that govern how they may interact in the world (Bluebond-Langner 1978), and are constantly in the process of distilling pertinent information to flesh out their wider social, political, and economic contexts to better situate their own experiences and to navigate potential futures (Abadía-Barrero 2011; Das 2015; Lee and De Finney 2005; Vindrola-Padros and Johnson 2014). There is agreement among researchers that children have agency (Bluebond-Langner and Korbin 2007) and actively engage in world-building through their participation in and with the world (Abadía-Barrero 2011; Das 2015; Toren 1993). There is also agreement that there are added benefits to recognizing children's perspectives in research as world-builders (Johnson 2011; Mitchell 2006a; Toren 1993). Some researchers have even advocated for the inclusion of young people's perspectives in the design and implementation of policy, recognizing the unique reflections young people are able to make about their own conditions of life (Blanchet-Cohen and Denov 2015; Vindrola-Padros, Pfister, and Johnson 2015). Ultimately, children are capable of meaningfully describing their worlds and are additionally capable of pulling into these descriptions and evaluations details that lie beyond the confines of their own immediate social

context. As noted by Lee and De Finney (2005) about the girls that participated in their popular theater-based project: “One important finding in our experience ... is that racialized girls do possess the knowledge to name their realities and to speak against their marginalization when given the opportunity to share and reflect on their experiences” (2005:110).

Using two plays written by girls and boys between the ages of 10 – 14, I discuss how children from low-income neighborhoods in Tegucigalpa and Comayagüela, Honduras, reflected on the status of public health during 2018-2019. Participants wrote the plays during a period of intense public debate about the quality and efficiency of public health care in Honduras (La Prensa 2018). These public debates eventually led to an auditing commission intervening the country’s flagship public teaching hospital in November of 2018 (SESAL 2018). In both plays, climactic scenes took place within the same public teaching hospital. Participants peppered their narratives with motifs suggestive of ongoing processes of material and social deterioration under capitalism (Stoler 2013) and summative scenes of *imaginal caring* (Hunleth 2019). In their plays, participants maneuvered deftly between representing the world as they experienced it, how it was presented to them, and creatively inserting new ways of thinking about the world (Shankar 2019). The plays described and analyzed here speak to the added value of being open to what children have to say on topics of health-disease processes that circle political, economic, and social tensions (Hunleth 2019), and the importance of incorporating new ways of producing knowledge about health-disease processes through artistic mediums (Valencia-Tobón 2016).

Conceptual tools employed to situate children as social commentators

Anthropologists of childhood warn against over-interpreting the words of children or failing to let children’s words and actions speak for themselves (James 2007). Still others caution against

over-interpreting the agency and independence of children when narrating their own worlds (Mitchell 2006b). In a recent article, Hunleth (2019) addresses some of those issues by acknowledging that although children may be bound by context, conditions of age and ongoing physical and intellectual development, they are also capable of commenting creatively and purposively on the worlds that appear to have control over them beyond “simplistic imitation ... or mere illusion or distortion of the social world” (Hunleth 2019:171). Through acts of play, Hunleth’s interlocutors shared how they “experienced collective concerns, frustrations, and uncertainties with illness and medicine from a position of relative powerlessness” (2019:171). Hunleth (2019) demonstrated that through play children could mobilize affect and engage in emotional acts of caring (which Hunleth terms *imaginal caring*), while making evident to others that they could both provide care and were deserving of care. During their play, the children elaborated on potential “what ifs” that allowed them to present alternate constructions of a shared social landscape in which they figured as meaningful participants devoted to the task of shaping new versions of ongoing experiences or shaping shared futures (Hunleth 2019).

I engaged my young participants in discussions about health and disease through writing and performing plays and through unscripted play. Following Schwartzman (1979), I think of play as “a contextual orientation towards something, which produces a text distinguished by allusion, distortion, and purported imitation” (as cited in Hunleth 2019:164). Some of that play happened through actual games that we played to get a handle on the factors affecting the distribution of health and disease in urban spaces; some occurred while we were drawing the background scenery for the plays that we wrote together; and almost all of it took place while writing the plays themselves and acting them out. In their plays, the children articulated larger health-disease processes and addressed themes that may be interpreted as reflective of an

ongoing “crisis” within the public health system, and indicative of their own, their families’ and their immediate networks’ experiences and responses.

Existing literature illustrates how children express experiences of structural violence (Abadía-Barrero 2011; Das 2015; Johnson 2011; Mitchell 2006b), but what struck me when reflecting on the children’s plays is how their expressions of structural violence were tempered by responses of care and solidarity. In this article, I draw out the relationship between these two from children’s perspectives through the concepts of *ruination* and *imaginal caring*. *Ruination* refers to the ongoing processes of material and subjective degradation that accompany capital accumulation and through which we can identify the workings of something we can call empire (Stoler 2013). *Ruination* is an acknowledgement that something called empire may be hard to locate in specific, bounded, and neat terms (or that it simply may not exist as an object), and that it may be more fruitful to refer to a set of processes that can be described and attributed, through their lingering visible and tangible effects, to “imperial formations” (Stoler 2013:11). These visible and tangible lingering effects are the ruins “people are left with” (Stoler 2013:9) when extractive “imperial formations” move on to a new global locale or extractive industry. Thus, the ruins that we are left with (e.g., defunct social welfare systems, urban infrastructural decay, internalized racism) turn into evidence of “processes of decimation, displacement, and reclamation” (Stoler 2013:8). *Ruination* is relevant to children’s experiences of structural violence for two reasons. First, addressing *ruination* forces us to engage with how people are made to live – and make lives – in the present, many times, in opposition to “state projects ... that are often strategic, nation building, and politically charged” (2013:21). Second, *ruination* provides an avenue to attribute ongoing processes of urban neglect and decay to political

economic projects that exceed our local spheres of influence, and which are historically constructed. To recognize ruins is part of the process of recognizing ruin-making.

Through *imaginal caring*, Hunleth (2019) provides us with tools to think about care in participants' plays alongside *ruination*. By *imaginal caring* (2019:159-160), Hunleth refers to forms of tending to others, showing affection, and requesting attention and recognition from others through both imagined acts and acts constructed or portrayed through images, or other forms of imagination-based engagements (2019:165). Hunleth notes that children are active, yet unacknowledged, figures in global health care work and consumers of "global health and humanitarian productions" (2019:163); as such, children are aware of ideals of care and keen to provide care for individuals on whom they depend and to show others that they can provide care. Through the imaginal, the children Hunleth engaged with in her research were able to "transcend the limits placed ... by their bodies, their relations, and their social locations" (2019:160), and to momentarily subvert the relations of power that determined their ability to act and that set limits on the care they were able to provide for others. The imaginal also provided an avenue for children to inspire actions in others towards them and to "encourage the types of behaviors and emotions they wanted to produce in their guardians" (2019:178). Through *imaginal caring*, children were able to announce to others their usually invisible care roles, their care needs, and to provide forms of care that exceeded their actual capabilities.

Through their plays, the children constructed different scenes of life in an urban context, and, per my request, constructed those scenes of life around their understanding of health-disease processes in Tegucigalpa and Comayagüela. Using the children's plays as a medium, I paused to reflect on how the children themselves reflected on the ways in which the people in their worlds – as reflected through the fictional worlds of the plays – labored to make livable spaces (Mitchell

2006a) in contexts marked by precarity and instability (Das 2015; Han 2012). Participants articulated social contexts littered with ruins and defined by material deterioration; however, they also articulated social responses within that material deterioration and decay against, perhaps, other forms of deterioration, most clearly expressed in unexpected (and at times magical) forms of care.

Background and Context

Honduras is a country located in Central America, and the Central District (CD) of Honduras (jointly composed of the cities of Tegucigalpa and Comayagüela) is roughly located in the south-central region of Honduras. According to the latest population census (INE 2013), Honduras had a total population of 8.3 million people, of which 1 million people resided in the CD. In the CD, 53 percent of the population was identified as female, and 75 percent of the population was under the age of 39. Eighty-eight percent of the population reported knowing how to read and write and 49 percent of the population had reached at least a ninth-grade education level (INE 2013). For Honduras as a whole, 42 percent of the population had one or more unmet basic needs (INE 2013), and 59.3 percent of households lived under the poverty line, out which 36.7% lived in extreme poverty (INE 2019). In the CD, specifically, 43 percent of the population lived in poverty, 20% of households were unable to meet daily subsistence needs, and 9 percent of households had crowded living conditions (INE 2013).

Honduran public health services were impacted by a recent history of instability and “crisis” and by the less recent adoption of neoliberal policies to satisfy geopolitical exigencies in the form of structural adjustment programs (Pine 2008; Barahona 2018). Under the guise of modernization, many national health systems across Latin America have been subjected to

transformation processes geared towards improving health service efficiency and efficacy (Cueto and Palmer 2014). Many of these changes began to take place during the 1990s, when the World Health Organization adopted institution-wide operational plans to mimic the health service models being proposed by the World Bank (Cueto and Palmer 2014). The Honduran national health system has been undergoing a so-called modernization/modernizing process since the early 1990s (PAHO 2009; Carmenate-Milán, Herrera-Ramos, and Ramos-Caceres 2016). Starting in 1990 and continuing up to the recent past, bilateral organizations, such as the Interamerican Development Bank, and large donors, like USAID, began to contribute funds and loans to the Honduran government earmarked for health sector reform (PAHO 2009; SESAL 2013). These reforms contemplated issues related to infrastructural (hard and soft) needs, but additionally, and perhaps more importantly, focused on decentralizing the large and fragmented public health sector (Carmenate-Milán et al. 2016). These changes first adopted in the 1990s gave way to decentralization processes in public health services during the following two decades (PAHO 2009; Bermúdez-Madriz, Seénz, Muiser, and Acosta 2011). In February 2010, Decree 286-2009 became law, and laid out what would become the foundation for the latest iteration of decentralization processes currently affecting multiple Honduran public sectors¹. In regard to the national health system, these decentralization measures were enshrined in several national health system plans associated with the conservative *Partido Nacional* in power between 2009-2021² (SEAL 2009, 2013, 2014), leading to a series of legislative changes from 2012 to the present (La Gaceta 2012, 2015, 2017, 2019) designed to increase the presence of private service providers in the national health system, while at the same time limiting the functions assigned to the national health system.

In November of 2018, through executive decree No. PCM-078-2018 (La Gaceta 2018), the conservative administration declared a state of emergency that led to the intervention of the public teaching hospital referenced above. Although the executive decree was intended to shore up the resources of a failing bulwark of the Honduran national health system, this decree cleared the path for private interests to stake a claim in public health management services to the detriment of a rapidly deteriorating public service. The executive decree of November 2018 was the culmination of a series of moments that composed the *ruination* of the national health system.

Methods

Data for this article were collected during 19 months of ethnographic fieldwork in Tegucigalpa, Honduras (November 2017 – June 2019). To write the plays, I worked with two different groups of children. I worked with one group of ten 10-year-old boys from an all-boys public school (*Gustavo Ponce*), and a group of 10 girls and boys between the ages of 10-14 from a mixed-gender public school (7 girls and 3 boys) (*Juana Pavón*)³. The boys from *Gustavo Ponce* were selected from between two 4th grade classes, and the girls and boys from *Juana Pavón* were selected from one single 6th grade class. I describe how the children were selected in the subsection *Participant Selection*. I selected the participating schools with the help of Mujeres en las Artes (MUA), a local, community-based organization that I partnered with to conduct this research. I secured permission from the Honduran Ministry of Education to carry out the project in the schools and from the respective school principals. I also obtained the informed consent of the parents of the children involved. Although the participant consent forms were signed by the parents, I informed both the parents and participating children about the project and their rights as participants. I also asked each child individually if they were interested in participating before

including them in the project. I let the children know repeatedly that their participation was voluntary and that they were free to participate, or not participate, to any extent which they saw fit as the project unfolded. MUA facilitated the approval from the Ministry of Education and the participation of the schools.

I first approached working with children as a way of getting closer to the worlds of adults, while acknowledging that children constituted an important segment of the Honduran urban population. Thirty-eight percent of the population of the CD was under the age of 18 (INE 2013). My initial idea was to train participants as researchers, by providing them with an understanding of the manifestation of health-disease processes in urban areas from the perspective of critical medical anthropology (Singer and Baer 1995) and some training in social science research techniques. During the early stages, I was mostly concerned with getting participants interested in the unequal distribution of health-disease processes and motivating them to want to collect data within their neighborhoods. Although we managed to write a survey instrument together and we talked about health-disease processes at length, very few of the participants were interested in conducting the surveys. My initial idea proved more complicated than I anticipated, but participants freely shared their own views on the world and things that mattered to them, especially when they were allowed to do so in a comfortable and somewhat loose context with few outward expectations, something that has been discussed in other research contexts with children (Thomas and O’Kane 2000; von Benzon 2015).

The idea of performing plays with the children was suggested by Verónica Romero (Vero). Vero was MUA’s communications’ director and my primary point of contact. The use of theater in public health is not new and has been adopted, for example, as tool for the development of health-policy (Nisker, Martin, Bluhm, and Daar 2006), as a tool for modeling health behavior (Ball

1994), or as a tool for challenging prevailing negative and discriminatory attitudes towards vulnerable populations (Pufahl, Rawat, Chaudary, and Shiff 2021). Other more interesting approaches, for the case at hand, have addressed the radical potential of including research participants in the development and production of plays by adopting research methodologies like Augusto Boal's "Theater of the Oppressed" (Lee and De Finney 2005; Saldaña 2005). In this latter example, participants engage with one another through a series of exercises to foster an intimate space in which delicate discussions on experience-near topics can take hold between participants. Then, participants develop short skits that labor to address the topics discussed in a manner that continues to foster discussion among participants.

I adopted Vero's suggestion but decided to steer away from theater as a public health tool for education and closer to theater as a tool for revelatory praxis by making research participants think about and write the plays themselves. The idea was that the children would then perform these plays in their schools for their peers. We were only able to perform one of the plays (*Gustavo Ponce*) in front of an audience. The audience was composed of some of the participants' parents and other MUA volunteers. In all, it was a crowd of about 20 people, and reception was generally positive, although I did not have the opportunity to engage with the parents to get a deeper sense of their thoughts. The day that we were meant to perform the play by the group from *Juana Pavón* at MUA's installations, only two of the participants showed up. The two participants from *Juana Pavón* that showed up had participated in every writing and practice session. When I asked if they knew what had happened to their colleagues, they just told me they did not know. Upon checking with the other participants during the following days, I was told some had forgotten, did not know about the session, or just did not feel like going to MUA that day. Although we rehearsed several

times as a group, we were unable to program an additional date that fit with MUA's or the participants' schedules.

The experiences that I share in this article constitute a *post-facto* reflection on inadvertently engaging with children as commentators on their worlds. The method that I employed and describe here (play writing) was not initially devised as a potential method or "imaginative research tool" (Johnson et al. 2012:165), but rather as a means of introducing an artistic creative element to my research project to better meld with the expectations of the local organization that was sponsoring my research: MUA. However, while working on the plays with the children, I believe we jointly engaged in acts of imagination or potentially productive free-flowing and non-consequential elaborations on non-existing scenarios (Sneath, Holbraad, and Pedersen 2009) that provided both commentary on actual worlds as experienced by the children (Hunleth 2011, 2019) and helped to construct future worlds by offering new (but not necessarily different) ways of viewing and understanding a present one (Toren 1993). While writing the plays, the children oriented themselves to the possible within the actual, leaving room for anything to take place, and that required being open to the different ways children create and share knowledge (Johnson et al. 2012).

Participant selection

Participants were selected using two different approaches. The boys from *Gustavo Ponce* were selected by the two teachers in charge of the two 4th grade classrooms, and the children who participated from *Juana Pavón* were selected by Vero and me. I decided to select participants from *Juana Pavón* with Vero's help to ensure that every student had an equal opportunity of

being selected to participate, since it was our impression that teachers from *Gustavo Ponce* favored those students whom they considered to be the best or the smartest for participation

I met with both groups of children independently over the course of three months between 2018 and 2019. My interactions with participants were structured around two main lines of engagement. During the first month and a half, my goal was to teach students about urban health inequalities from the perspective of critical medical anthropology (Singer and Baer 1995). These sessions took place at each school during regular class periods for three non-consecutive hours a week. The following month and a half, I met with students at MUA's offices over longer periods of time, where we jointly developed a script on a health-related topic. During the second month and a half, my meetings with students took place outside of school hours and really depended on the student's overall interest in meeting with me or their ability to do so, given other competing demands. Attendance was irregular for both groups, but there was usually a core group of four or five participants in each group that always attended our joint sessions.

During our sessions devoted to the play and the play writing process, participants selected amongst themselves the topic for their play, developed the idea, determined the cast of characters, and wrote the dialogue. I did my best to remain an observer and moderator throughout the sessions, mostly reminding participants to focus on a locally relevant health issue, identifying potential holes in their plots, and asking questions during our tabletop sessions to help move the story forward. However, I certainly asked participants to remain mindful of what they had learned about the unequal distribution of health and disease in society and the social, political, material, and administrative barriers that perpetuated such inequality (Singer and Baer 1995). Both groups produced one short five to ten-minute play that introduced some health issue in a way that was significant to the structure of the play.

Play writing

The process of selecting the major theme of the play and defining the overall structure of the story was different with both groups. With the boys from *Gustavo Ponce*, I asked all the participants to write a short story, consisting of two paragraphs, where they discussed some relevant concern with health and disease in the CD. After they finished writing their stories, each one of them read it to the other participants, and after having listened to their peers' stories, they voted on their favorite one. With the group from *Juana Pavón*, I decided to take a more collective and interactive approach. I sat with participants in an empty classroom at their school and asked them to start brainstorming ideas on a play that they would like to write and perform. As they spoke, I wrote down their ideas on a whiteboard with a black marker. I wrote down their ideas on plot, characters, progression, conflict, and resolution. For each one of these, I would ask them to pause until everyone that wanted to say something could give their opinion, and when everyone appeared satisfied (or unsatisfied participants had been outvoted), we moved on. By the end of both exercises, we had agreed upon the basic structure of the play that we would then flesh out during our sessions at MUA.

I tried to approach writing the plays with both groups the same way. To write the dialogue, we would all sit around a table, and I would ask all the participants to pitch ideas for dialogue with our already established basic premise in mind. As the participants talked about possible dialogue, I would write down their suggestions on blank sheets of paper and then I would read it back to them. If all the participants agreed with the dialogue, nobody objected, or nobody thought changes were necessary, I would ask them to continue pitching dialogue. We would do this for 30-45 minutes at each one of our sessions, which is usually how long it took

for participants to become bored or simply lose interest in the activity. To prepare for the next session, I would write the dialogue down on new blank sheets of paper, make photocopies, and distribute them to participants at the beginning of the following session. Before retaking the writing process, we would always perform a table read of the dialogue, as it was written up to that point, and then we would begin the process again. While writing, I continually referred to the basic premises we had previously agreed upon as a group, mostly to maintain some semblance of direction and order. If not, the participants would have probably been amenable to starting a new story pretty much every time we sat down to write.

Local Challenges to the Playwriting Process

I conducted this part of my research with the boys from *Gustavo Ponce* first. After a month and half of learning about health-disease processes, I could tell they were beginning to grow weary with our encounters. To regain their interest and attention, I decided to switch gears and to begin focusing on the play that I had committed to creating both to meet MUA's interests in demonstrating the value of re-introducing the arts into the public-school curriculum, and to meet the school principals' expectations of producing content that could be used to model "good" health behavior for other students. The first session that I held with the children on performance and prop design was conducted by a local actor, playwright, and member of the National School for the Performing Arts (ENBA). During that weeklong session, Fabricio Raudales taught participants about the history of theater and began to show them how to make their own puppets to put on a puppet show. During this encounter, I could see how the children, again, got interested in what we were doing together and began to participate actively once more. In that series of moments, I decided to just focus on the play, feeling that I owed participants the

opportunity to enjoy themselves after being subjected to my research agenda for so long. By the time I started working with the group from *Juana Pavón*, I had already realized that the real productive aspect of this exercise with the children lay in the play writing process, and I altered my expectations and goals accordingly.

Both groups of children presented their own unique sets of challenges to work with. The process of writing was, at times, frustratingly slow. With both groups, writing a page of dialogue, around 150 words, could take anywhere between 5 minutes to half an hour, and I began to divide our time between writing for 30-45 minutes and letting them draw or work on scenery or just hang out for just as long, if not more, depending on the participant or simply the day. Progress was slow and uncertain, and each time I felt myself getting frustrated, I would re-evaluate my goals, loosen my expectations, and remind myself that I wanted all of us to enjoy what we were doing together; that also meant letting myself enjoy it without expecting something specific to come out of the process. I ended up drawing with both groups a lot, watching short videos on social media platforms, eating a lot of junk food, and I even made my own puppet. Overall, working with the children within the school setting was more difficult than working with them at MUA's installations. At MUA, I felt both the children and I were freer to do what we wanted, and it was also easier to provide all the participants with snacks and a hearty lunch. All this helped to break up our sessions into more rewarding and manageable chunks of time.

The Plays

In what follows, I provide a summary of each play written by the two groups of children. I follow both descriptions with a joint analysis of what the children were inviting peers to think through with them, as well as potential spectators.

Gustavo Ponce, "A family in need"

The play begins under one of the many bridges found across Tegucigalpa and Comayagüela, where the family in the story lives. The protagonist of the story is the youngest son of a family of four. The day begins like any other until the youngest son starts complaining about a persistent headache. At first, his parents suspect that the youngest child may have contracted dengue fever, until their son unexpectedly faints and collapses to the floor. A physician, who happens to be walking over the bridge at the same moment the son collapses, hears the mother's screams and the ensuing commotion, and ventures under the bridge to investigate what is happening. The physician is alarmed by the unresponsive child and helps the family rush the patient to a well-known public hospital, where he also happens to be employed part-time. On the way to the hospital, the ambulance that was transporting the son almost gets into an accident because it was being chased by the camera crew for a local news and entertainment channel. Once at the hospital, the same physician that initially assisted the family under the bridge informs the family that the son has a brain tumor. The physician also informs the family that it is possible to remove the tumor, but that the operation is expensive, and that the public institution can neither perform the procedure nor cover the cost. In other words, if the family wants the operation, they will have to cover all the expenses for the procedure at a private facility. At a loss for what to do, the father decides to walk out of the emergency room into the waiting area to get some air. In the waiting room he is accosted by a news reporter, a member of the same crew that almost caused the ambulance to crash earlier in the play. The father turns to the reporter and explains what he has just learned about his son's health and about the very costly operation. The reporter then turns to the camera and proceeds to ask the show's viewership to help the family. A millionaire happens

to be watching the show and decides to help. The millionaire shows up at the hospital almost immediately, arranges transfer to a private facility, and ensures that the procedure is conducted. The youngest son wakes up several weeks later without a tumor and in a new house, which happens to be attached to the millionaire's residential compound. Not only does the millionaire pay for the very costly operation, but he also provides the family with a house and a monthly allowance. The family, and their newest millionaire family member, live happily ever after.

Juana Pavón, "Untitled"

The play begins during dinner time in a relaxed household atmosphere. The mother calls her three children, who are bickering and generally being siblings, to the dinner table. As they are sitting down to eat, they hear a loud knock on the front door. All four freeze. The mother hesitates as to whether she should open the door. We hear someone knock at the door again, only this time followed by a man's voice demanding to be let in. The mother finally opens the door and her husband walks in, drunk. The three children make excuses to leave the room. The mother and father stay in the main room arguing. Off-scene, we hear the mother scream, as if in pain, and almost immediately we hear the door slam shut. The children race into the room again – as do two neighbors that had been keeping an eye on the situation – to find out what happened. The neighbors, two women, confront the mother about what the viewers are led to believe is recurrent domestic abuse. The mother claims it was an accident. The husband/father spends the rest of the night drinking and is later beaten up outside of a bar by a group of unknown strangers. The strangers claim that it is in retaliation for what he did to his wife earlier in the evening. Four *Cristianas* [*Christians*] that were leaving their *culto* [*worship*] see the strangers beating up the husband/father and rush to his aid as the strangers disperse. The women call an ambulance to

take the injured man to the hospital – a wheelbarrow with a siren shows up instead. Once in the hospital, one of the *Cristianas* gets the contact information for next of kin and contacts the wife/mother. The wife receives a call from the *Cristiana* while she is out in the city with her three children collecting cans and plastic bottles to exchange for cash so that they can get something to eat. Upon ending the phone call, the woman rushes with her children to the hospital. At the hospital, the wife is taken into the room where her husband is lying under observation, but the husband is momentarily unconscious and unable to speak. The wife leaves the room and speaks to the attending physician who informs her he must spend the night under observation. That same night the husband is visited by a mysterious woman, and he is awakened by this mysterious woman stroking his legs. At first, he is startled, but then starts flirting with the woman. The woman flirts at first, but then transforms into a specter – *La Llorona*⁴ – and tells the father that she is going to abduct one of his children for being a neglectful father and an abusive husband. The woman disappears and the father rushes out of bed to look for his wife, who has been waiting all night in the waiting room with their children. They realize one of the kids is missing and begin to search the hospital until they find the youngest child. They find the unconscious child outside one of the bathrooms but generally unharmed. The father vows to change and in the final scene we discover that the father has stopped drinking, has secured stable employment, and that all five are living together happily. It is worth mentioning that the participants explained *La Llorona*'s presence inside the hospital, during our tabletop discussions, by noting that she had committed suicide at the hospital after her own two children died from dengue fever while admitted at the same hospital.

On Care in Ruination

In their plays, participants from both schools addressed something that could be a window into *ruination* within the Honduran public health system. The most emblematic public hospital in the country was a notable site of interaction in the plays and one which could be thought of as representing ongoing processes of privatization and capitalist accumulation spearheaded by private interests intimately intertwined with public power (Waitzkin and Jasso-Aguilar 2015). In other words, the hospital was a prime site of infrastructural decay and neglect. However, the hospital itself was not the only “ruin” through which participants explored *ruination*, participants also called our attention to the conditions under which both families portrayed in the plays carried out their daily lives. Both families occupied what could be termed “interior frontiers” (Gidwani 2018), urban spaces within which undue force and control is exerted over the populations and individuals that sustain capitalist projects; entire groups of people systematically dispossessed, exposed to environmental decay, and classed as necessary casualties in the intractable process of wealth extraction and future-building (Povinelli 2011). The family in the first play lived under a bridge next to a polluted river – which the boys playfully indicated by coloring the river a deep purple – and the family in the second play labored in the poorly paid and dangerous waste collection system that makes life in cities possible across multiple levels (Gidwani 2018).

The evocations of *ruination* in both plays were not limited to the infrastructural, but perhaps also evident across subjective domains through the presence of specters and miraculous acts. Through ghosts and the miraculous, participants were collectively thinking about topics that were generally difficult to think about (Pinto 2018) and participating in subversions of an established order, elaborating on “what ifs” by, for example, reconfiguring a local myth⁵ (i.e., *La Llorona*), and by challenging the inveterateness of local class-based conflict and indifference

(i.e., the millionaire). By introducing these characters, the participants opened the possibility to thinking about what care can/could be like in *ruination*, but, perhaps, the participants were also introducing the challenging notion that care was not possible, or hard to provide, under *ruination*. Take, for example, *La Llorona*.

The presence of *La Llorona* in the second play redirects our attention to a powerful act of subjective violence with which the play began, but which is never truly resolved, an act of subjective violence which contained larger acts of structural violence (Zizek 2008). Violence against women in Honduras is almost twice as high as reported elsewhere in Latin America, is significantly concentrated in urban areas, and manifests most frequently within the home and between family members (UNDP 2020). Furthermore, reports of domestic violence in Honduras doubled between 2017 to 2019 (UNDP 2020:6) and sexual violence against girls was concentrated in the 10 – 14 age group during 2019 (UNDP 2020:7). In the play written by students from *Juana Pavón*, the mother never receives care – in the relational sense offered by Eva Kittay (2016) – from the state or from others, unless we consider the intervention from *La Llorona* as an act of care. On the other hand, the father/husband is cared for by two separate sets of strangers with fixed and loose ties to institutions: hospital staff and the *Cristianas*. This care was provided on top of the care already being provided to the father/husband by the mother/wife and their children. At the same time, *La Llorona*'s own personal tragedy and presence at the hospital was orchestrated by processes of institutional neglect and socially produced precarity that coalesced while trying to secure care for her own children through established public health services. Going back to Kittay (2016), *La Llorona* may exemplify how the children dealt with the complicated reality that being able to provide care for others is deeply impacted by structurally conditioned socioeconomic possibilities and social positions, and how that may lie in

tension with a continued desire or aspiration to provide care for others despite existing barriers. In the first play, the boys from *Gustavo Ponce* also appealed to a similarly otherworldly character, the millionaire, who also drove a wedge between expectations of the type of care that should be provided by public health services and the undeniably unfolding reality that public health services were being replaced by private parties and interests and new ways of conceiving what obtaining care may look like. It is equally notable that in their conception of care and their search for a resolution, the boys from *Gustavo Ponce* looked beyond public health services instead of providing a resolution that remained within the public domain.

Although the children's elaboration of *La Llorona* and the millionaire in their plays may have been composed in attention to *ruination* in the Honduran public health system, they should also be taken as evidence that the children were aware of the complexity of their social worlds and how these were sustained through multiple acts of social solidarity, many of which escape public scrutiny by being folded into everyday acts and relations of care (Das 2015; Han 2012). Some of those acts of care were evident and straight forward in the plays, as in the doctor assisting the family in the first play or the neighbors being attentive to the mother in the second. Others were more jarring and unexpected, but nevertheless, within the realm of the possible for participants. Perhaps, these "fantastical" and "exaggerated" accounts, could be conceived of as a mechanism the participants used to think *through* (Pinto 2018) their own exposure to and experiences with concealed acts of care or as a means to "invert" their usual powerlessness. Through these characters, they "conjured care" to "push back against external and deeply unequal global power structures in a place where care ... was both critical for biological and social survival and difficult to accomplish" (Hunleth 2019:160). Far from producing wholly negative or disparaging portrayals of life and health in Tegucigalpa and Comayagüela,

participants “conjured care” through characters that evoked hope, aspirations, and belief in the possibility of a more stable and desirable future amid a complicated present: the *Cristianas*, the pedestrian doctor, the nurses, and even *La Llorona* and the millionaire.

In the plays, all these figures intercede on behalf of strangers without any – at least overt – expectation of a reward or benefit. Although *La Llorona* enacted subjective violence, that act was meant as corrective to other acts of structurally reproduced violence (e.g., domestic violence, alcoholism, neglect). The *Cristianas*, in turn, may have prevented serious injury to the father and played an integral role in helping the father continue to be a part of his own family. The *Cristianas* evoked, as it was explained to me by one of the participants, an idea of inherent goodness that was enacted by other characters in that same play, and that were also present in the first play. For example, the father in the second play was capable of change and his family’s life was similarly altered. In the first play, the millionaire mobilized to respond to the imminent material needs of the family and the family, in turn, may have provided for the millionaire’s immanent needs by adopting him into their family. Through their plays, participants also “conjured care” that presented the possibility of different futures. Portrayals of *ruination* within the public health system were accompanied by a sense of solidarity, and a sense that characters’ needs and expectations exceeded that which could, at the moment and owing to these same processes of *ruination*, be provided by the public institutions portrayed in the plays. Through their plays, the children seemed to envelope the failures of the public health system into a complex social fabric alerting to existing failures, describing modes of potentially existing social support, and recognizing the centrality of (in spite of if all) still functioning public health services, while, unfortunately, constructing a dismal future for the continued existence of these same necessary public health services.

Conclusion

The plays described here show that children can comment creatively and critically on their worlds, if provided with the space to do so imaginatively (Thomas and O’Kane 2000; Mitchell 2006a; Johnson et al. 2012). Through their plays, the children articulated their understandings of local health-disease processes and provided a glimpse of how their understandings and experiences of public health were shaped by local political-economic contexts and histories. Participants portrayed how they experienced *ruination* in the public health system and were able to construct a complicated picture of care that intermingled spaces of social solidarity with an uncertainty over whether or not that solidarity could/would obtain and from who/where.

Unlike in Hunleth’s research example (2019), participants in my research did not insert themselves within the worlds they constructed in their plays and as such did not directly construct the play as a mode of caring for others or asking others to care for them. However, as Hunleth (2019) notes, “part of giving care and also receiving care back...was doing things to make others act and feel ... an intervention into the present with implications for the future” (2019:180). In that sense, the girls and boys that participated in my research demonstrated how the well-being of children in the scenes that they constructed were dependent on the attitudes and well-being of others in their lives with varying degrees of power over their own immediate life circumstances. In doing so, participants also affirmed their own expectations for future practices of care in contexts and scenarios like those which they depicted, indicated their own overarching

concern with the ongoing deterioration of existing public health services, and grappled with their own uncertainty over how their future care needs in *ruination* could be or would be met.

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Notes

¹ Decreto No. 286-2009, “Poder legislativo decreta: Ley para el establecimiento de una Visión de País y la adopción de un Plan de Nación para Honduras,” Diario Oficial La Gaceta, 02/02/2010.

² Porfirio Lobo Sosa came to power in 2010 after presidential elections in 2009 largely boycotted by opposition movements in response to the *coup* against José Manuel Zelaya Rosales on 28 June 2009 (CIDH 2009).

³ The school names are pseudonyms. Juana Pavón (1945-2019) was a Honduran feminist poet and social critic. Gustavo Ponce, PhD, (1956-2010) was a Guatemalan astrophysicist who lived and worked in Honduras.

⁴ “La Llorona” is a myth with wide diffusion across Latin America with possible pre-Hispanic roots (Martos Garcia and Martos Garcia 2015).

⁵ Contrary to the actual myth (Martos Garcia and Martos Garcia 2015), *La Llorona* in the second play did not murder her own children.

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